

ON THE HISTORICITY OF THE PERIOD OF THE SHAYBANIS

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The Shaibani state is a state existing in the territories of present-day Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, southern Kazakhstan, northern Afghanistan, and southeastern Turkmenistan. It is known that Muhammad Shaybani began to conquer Movarounnahr in 1499, and in 1500-1501 he conquered Samarkand and declared it the capital of his state. In 1507, he finally established his authority over all of Movarounnahr and Khorasan.

The period of the rule of the Shaybanites was characterized by prosperity. Under them, some of the unique masterpieces of the Middle Ages were built. The rulers made a significant contribution to the development of historiography during the Shaybani period. Basically, the development of historiography is related to factors such as political stability, cultural relations, scientific and literary environment. The works written during the Shaibani period mainly cover the following aspects: historical events, personalities and cultural heritage. During this period, thoughts about historical problems and their causes, various historical methods and theories were developed.

In the era of Shaibani, historiography is not limited to collecting historical facts, but also focuses on analyzing historical events, evaluating them and showing their interrelationships. This, in turn, created the ground for a more in-depth study of the history of our nation. The majority of Shaybanis were educated and paid great attention to science and culture.

In particular, Shaibanis such as Muhammad Shaybani Khan, Kochkunchi Khan, Ubaidullah Khan, Rustam Sultan, Abdulaziz Khan, and Javanmardali Sultan wrote poems in Turkish and Persian, and had sufficient potential in religious and secular sciences. In particular, the libraries belonging to Abdulaziz Khan and Abdullah Khan II were considered the largest book treasures of their time, they were also engaged in copying, repairing and decorating manuscripts [1:252].

History was considered one of the most developed fields during the Shaibani period.

For example, during this period, "Tawarihi Guzida-Nusratnama", "Fathnama" by Mulla Shadi, "Zubdat al-asrar" by Abdullah Nasrullah,

"Mehmonnomayi Bukhara" by Fazlullah Rozbekhan, "Badoye al-Waqoe" by Zayniddin Wasifi, "Abdullanama" by Hafiz Tanish al-Bukhari. such major historical works were created. These works give us important information about the social and political life of the Shaibani era, mutual feudal wars and other important social and political events [1:252].

"Tawarihi guzida-Nusratnoma" ("Selected stories-Victory book") is a work written in the old Uzbek language, which mainly tells about the history of our country at the beginning of the 16th century. The work is written in Chigatai Turkish and is an anonymous source dedicated to the history of Shaybani Khan. There are various disputes among researchers about the author of the work. Some consider him Bahauddin Walid, others Muhammad Salih. However, regardless of the identity of the author, this book is considered one of the valuable works describing the history of the peoples of Central Asia.

The work is a valuable source of history, ethnography, art, language and literature of Uzbek and other Central Asian peoples of the XV-XVI centuries. This work is necessary for philologists and linguists who study the history of the formation and development of the Uzbek language and literature, especially for historians and source historians studying the period of the Mongols, Timurids, and especially the Shaibani period. The reason is that this monument has not yet been sufficiently studied by experts and has not been involved in research.

It also briefly describes the history of Oghuz Khan and Alankuva, that is, the ancient history of the Turkic peoples, the reign of Genghis Khan and the Timurid dynasty. The most valuable part of the work from the point of view of the narrative of historical events is the history of Abulhairkhan and Shaibanikhan, which is directly written by the author. As we mentioned above, the author of the work is unknown, but it is known from the text itself that Shaibani Khan was one of the palace historians, and the fact that it was written by his direct commission is stated at the very beginning: I was the reason... the king of Muazzam Sahib as-Saif wal Qalam Imam Az-Zaman and Caliph When ar-Rahman held the highest honor, suppressed the state, took the province of Movarunnahr, killed him on the throne of the state and happiness, and made the sermon and siqqa (coin) with the name of imam az-zaman and caliph ar-Rahman, blessed. I came to the memory, until one night I selected from the histories and one night I gathered the words into a circle of order. let the king of Kishwaristan know the truth and the meaning of the gift of his generation." Currently, there is not a single perfect copy of "Tawarihi guzida-Nusratnama" [2:456].

Another important source related to the Shaybani era is the work "Fathnama", which is divided into two parts: "Muqaddimah", which talks about the history of the period before Timur in general, and "Zafarnama", the main part, which covers the history of Timur's era. The work was written by Mulla Shadi in 1502 on the order of Mahmud Sultan. From the day Muhammad Shaybani was born to June 1501, the important political and military events that took place in the Uzbek nation and the Movarounnahr region are widely covered. The work describes Muhammad Shaybani's military operations in Turkestan, Andijan, Bukhara and Karshi regions, as well as his skill in marshalling troops. It was determined that there are 5 copies of the work in world libraries [4:264].

The next source is the historical work "Zubdat ul-asar" ("Work of Chronicles"). The author was Shaybani historian Abdullah Nasrullahi or Abdullah ibn Muhammad ibn Ali Nasrullah.

Abdullah Nasrullahi is a historian and scientist from Balkh who lived in the second half of the 15th century and the first half of the 16th century. In the 80s and 90s of the 15th century, the historian was in the service of Badiuzzamon Mirzo, the governor of Balkh in the Timurid region. After Herat was occupied by Shaibani Khan in 1507, he entered his service. After the death of Muhammad Shaibani Khan in 1510, his son Muhammad Temur came to Samarkand. Later, Abdulla Nasrullahi Shaibani came to Tashkent with the sultans and went to the service of Suyunchhoja Khan. Shortly after that, the son of the historian Suyunchhoja Khan, the governor of Shahrukhiya, was hired by Sultan Muhammad, also known as Keldi Muhammad, and in 1525 he wrote his book "Zubdat ul-asar" on his behalf.

"Zubdat ul-asar" is written in the direction of general history and includes socio-political events that took place in Muslim countries from ancient times to 1525. In it, the events that took place in Khorasan and Movarounnahr in the first quarter of the 16th century are covered in some detail. Especially the ongoing armed struggle between Shaybani sultans Kochkunchikhan, Jonibek Sultan, Ubaydullah Khan, Muhammad Temur Sultan and Babur Mirza and his political allies Safavids for Movarunnahr, and Suyunchhoja and Sultan Said Khan for the crown in the middle of 1512-1514. struggle is depicted.

"Abdullanoma" ("Sharafnomayi Shahi") is a historical work dedicated to the history of Movarounnahr in the 16th century. It was written in Persian by Hafiz Tanish Bukhari between 1584 and 1590. The work is dedicated to the ruler of Bukhara, Abdullah Khan II, and is called "Sharafnomayi Shahi" and some

abridged copies are also called "Zafarnomayi Abdullah Khan". The work is written in mixed rhymed prose and consists of an introduction, two articles (parts) and conclusions. But it is not known when the last part of the work was finished. In the introduction to the work, the political events that took place in Movarounnahr before Abdullah Khan came to power - the invasion of Genghis Khan and the rule of the Mongols, the establishment of the state of Abul Khair Khan (1428-1468) in Dashti Kipchak, the marches of Shaybani Khan (1451-1510) to Khorasan, the military conflicts between the Shaybani and Zahiruddin Babur, and It is told about the lineage and lineage of Abdullah Khan [7:44,45].

In short, the historiography of the Shaibani period made a great contribution to the cultural and political history of Uzbekistan. There is no doubt that the works written during this period serve as an important source for modern historiography. Historians of the period under study tried not only to record the events, but also to analyze them and teach them to future generations

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